

Research papers

Parametrized physics-informed deep operator networks for Design of Experiments applied to Lithium-Ion-Battery cells

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ABSTRACT

Model-based state estimation of lithium-ion batteries relies on a robust, yet efficient parametrization of the underlying model under different conditions, which can be analyzed and improved through the lenses of Design-of-Experiments (DoE) methodologies. This paper presents parametrized physics-informed deep operator networks (PI-DeepONets) trained without any measured or synthetic data to predict solutions of a Single-Particle-Model for varying current profiles and electrode-specific diffusivity values. The prediction accuracy is evaluated based on three use cases representing three sets of current profiles featuring constant, smoothly time-dependent and non-smooth pulse profiles. After training PI-DeepONets, lithium concentration profiles are predicted within milliseconds achieving normalized percentage errors on the particle surfaces below 0.3% for constant or smoothly time-dependent current profiles and below 2% for non-smooth pulse profiles. The fast approximation of Fisher-Information-Matrices (FIMs) based on the trained PI-DeepONets offers additional speed-up potentials for DoE methodologies and yields a speed-up factor of 30 in the considered use case when compared to classical FIM approximation via finite differences on numerical reference solutions.

1. Introduction

Lithium-Ion-Batteries (LIBs) are a crucial part of many technological initiatives that aim at the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in transportation, energy storage and other areas of society where harmful contributions to climate change have been identified in the past. Despite their promising properties in terms of efficiency and sustainability, LIB cells and corresponding battery systems require a lot of time and money in research & development (R&D) due to the increasing demands in terms of energy density and costs from industry and private customers. Consequently, fast and accurate simulations of LIBs are required to cut down time and costs of physical testing in the development of advanced materials and safer designs, and to increase the understanding and predictability of the complex electrochemical processes unfolding inside LIBs, e.g., during cell aging.

In the past decades, several modeling approaches have been developed to simulate LIB cells, in most cases given by partial differential equations (PDEs) that describe the diffusion and reaction processes of lithium inside the cell. These models range from coarse models with several simplifications like the Single-Particle-Model with or without electrolyte dynamics (SPMe/SPM) to more advanced models like the one introduced in 1993 by Doyle, Fuller and Newman (DFN) [1].

Marquis et al. [2] provide an extensive comparison of the aforementioned models and their trade-offs with respect to runtime and accuracy when different C-rates are applied to the cell during charging and discharging.

A common issue in application of these models in both R&D and on-board monitoring of state variables like State-of-Charge (SoC) or State-of-Health (SoH) in Battery-Management-Systems (BMS) is the difficulty of identifying model parameters from the available measurement data. This is due to the fact that the internal state variables like lithium concentrations and electrochemical potentials cannot be measured and validated in realistic applications and instead, only external state variables like current, voltage and temperature are available. Rojas et al. [3] have given a thorough overview on several models and their identifiability in this context and a recent review by Andersson et al. [4] highlights the importance of a thorough and holistic approach to non-destructive model parametrization including global sensitivity analyses and methodologies for the Design of Experiments (DoE). For the latter, Roman-Ramirez et al. [5] provided an extensive review on DoE methodologies applied to LIB cells. In this context, the DoE for model parametrization aims to provide insights into which experiment, e.g., current profiles, maximizes the identifiability

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of parameters through the measurable outputs. Several works have shown that the systematic evaluation and optimization of input profiles, e.g., in terms of Fisher-Information-Matrices (FIMs), can improve the parametrization of LIB models [6–8]. However, an immanent issue of many model-based DoE approaches is the high computational effort as the underlying models may have to be solved for a large number of parameter combinations and input profiles. This is further emphasized in recent work by Streb et al. [9] who highlight the benefit of a global DoE approach for parameter identification at the cost of additional computational efforts. Depending on the chosen model and application scenario, these efforts can become intractable and simplifications, e.g., via Reduced-Order-Modeling (ROM), need to be considered.

Among these, the more recent advancements of Machine Learning (ML) offer promising frameworks that allow a much faster inference of model responses after the optimization process (often referred to as “training”). In 2019, Raissi et al. [10] introduced the notion of Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs), which combine the inference speed of neural networks with an explicit and data-free supervision based on the underlying physical equations. While this classical PINN approach aims at the solution of single (PDE) problems, the notion of Operator Learning – e.g., achieved via Deep Operator Networks (DeepONets) [11] or their physics-informed adaption (PI-DeepONets) [12] – aims at the approximation of a mapping between two function spaces. In context of (physics-informed) Operator Learning, the input functions to be learned commonly represent different initial or boundary conditions [13].

In the field of battery modeling, data-driven or hybrid approaches have been proposed frequently, cf., e.g., [14–17]. More specifically related to this work, Zheng et al. [18] introduced a composite model built from several hybrid and data-driven DeepONets to predict voltage responses for different diffusivity values and linear dynamic current profiles in a differentiable framework that can be effectively used for parameter inference in an on-board scenario. In follow-up work [19], an adaption of DeepONet featuring multiple inputs (MIONet) aims at resolving both boundary and initial condition as inputs to the model with a user-defined step size but is only capable of generalizing over constant current functions. Hassanaly et al. [20,21] have shown the applicability of classical PINNs for both the SPM and the DFN model by applying hierarchical training and an architecture tailored towards the physical relations between model inputs and outputs. Their models are trained for individual dynamic current profiles, analyzed in terms of data dependence and a Bayesian framework is presented for a more realistic view on the parametrization process.

To the best of our knowledge, all previous work in the field of PINNs for battery modeling is (a) limited in terms of the current diversity during training (either fixed or generalized over constant or linear dynamic currents) or (b) dependent on data, which causes concerns due to the curse of dimensionality for high-dimensional parameter domains that are required in realistic parameter identification scenarios. This paper aims at closing the gaps between the aforementioned works and highlights the potential of PI-DeepONets in global DoE methodologies for LIB model parametrization. Its specific contributions are summarized as follows:

- Introduction of a purely physics-driven parametrized PI-DeepONet architecture as fast surrogate model which outperforms existing approaches in terms of the diversity of considered current profiles as well as its independence from any measured or synthetic data.
- Benchmarking of several architectural variations of parametrized PI-DeepONets trained on varying boundary conditions and a parameter domain spanning two orders of magnitude per parameter.
- Demonstrating the potential of parametrized PI-DeepONets for application in global DoE methodologies due to the fast and accurate approximation of gradient information after training.

Fig. 1. Single-Particle-Model (SPM).

2. Methodology

In this section, we state the SPM as the underlying model to this work and introduce the physics-informed neural network architecture that is trained to solve the SPM for different boundary conditions and sets of parameter values.

2.1. Single-Particle-Model (SPM)

The SPM, cf. [22] and Fig. 1, models the lithium diffusion inside a LIB cell approximated by a single spherically symmetric particle per electrode. The underlying PDE derived from Fick’s law of diffusion is given for both cathode ($j = p$) and anode ($j = n$) as

$$\frac{\partial c_j(r, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(D_j r^2 \frac{\partial c_j(r, t)}{\partial r} \right), \quad j \in \{n, p\}, \quad (1)$$

where c_j denotes the lithium concentration in the solid particles. The spatio-temporal domain is composed by the radial component $r \in [0, R_j]$ with particle radii R_j and a given time interval $t \in [0, t_{\max}]$. D_j denotes the solid phase lithium diffusivity in each electrode. Based on a time-dependent current $I(t)$ applied to the battery cell, complementary boundary conditions are given at the particle center and surface as

$$\frac{\partial c_j(r, t)}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=0} = 0, \quad j \in \{n, p\}, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial c_j(r, t)}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=R_j} = \frac{I(t)}{A L_j F D_j a_j}, \quad j \in \{n, p\}, \quad (3)$$

where A denotes the electrode surface area, L_j the electrode thickness, a_j the specific interfacial area, and F Faraday’s constant. In this work, the model is completed by assuming a constant initial condition given as

$$c_j(r, 0) = c_j^0, \quad j \in \{n, p\}. \quad (4)$$

Based on [2] and due to the neglect of electrolyte dynamics in the standard SPM, the time-dependent voltage response of the battery cell can be approximated from the resulting surface concentrations $c_j^{\text{surf}}(t) = c_j(R_j, t)$ and the current profile $I(t)$ as follows:

$$V(t) = U_p^{\text{OCP}} \left(c_p^{\text{surf}}(t) \right) - U_n^{\text{OCP}} \left(c_n^{\text{surf}}(t) \right) + \eta_r(t), \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_r(t) = -\frac{2RT}{F} \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{I(t)}{a_p j_{0,p} L_p} \right) - \frac{2RT}{F} \sinh^{-1} \left(\frac{I(t)}{a_n j_{0,n} L_n} \right), \quad (6)$$

$$j_{0,j} = (c_j^{\text{surf}})^{\frac{1}{2}} (c_j^{\text{max}} - c_j^{\text{surf}})^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (7)$$

where R denotes the universal gas constant and T the temperature. The material-dependent open circuit potentials U_p^{OCP} and U_n^{OCP} and over-reaction potential η_r are derived according to [2]. All model parameters in the SPM including open circuit potentials are based on the work by Chen et al. [23] who experimentally determined and validated a parameter set for an LGM50 cell at beginning of life. The reader is referred to Table A.1 in the Appendix for a detailed description of these parameters.

2.2. Physics-Informed Deep Operator Networks (PI-DeepONets)

In this section, we introduce variations of PI-DeepONets that are trained to predict solutions of the SPM for different current profiles $I(t)$ and sets of diffusivity parameters (D_n, D_p) within the spatio-temporal domain introduced in Section 2.1. In their original formulation, cf. [11, 13], PI-DeepONets are composed of two fully-connected subnetworks. One to encode varying functional inputs (here: $I(t)$) referred to as “branch” and one to encode the coordinate and parameter space (here: (r, t, D_n, D_p)) referred to as “trunk”. Throughout this work, we refer to this architecture as “Standard” PI-DeepONet. In the following, the physics-informed training scheme is introduced which is driven by the non-dimensionalized formulation of Eqs. (1)–(4) and two modifications are proposed with respect to “Standard” in terms of Fourier feature embeddings and trunk architecture, respectively.

2.2.1. Physics-informed training

Nondimensionalization. As it is commonly advised for the training of PINNs, cf. [24], all PI-DeepONets considered in this work are trained by minimizing the residuals of the nondimensionalized formulation of the SPM based on the scaled dimensionless quantities

$$\bar{r}_j = \frac{r}{r_j^*}, \bar{t}_j = \frac{t}{t_j^*}, \bar{c}_j = \frac{c_j}{c_j^*}. \quad (8)$$

Choosing $r_j^* = R_j$ and $c_j^* = c_n^{\text{max}}$ allows sampling from a single nondimensionalized radial domain $\bar{r}_j \in [0, 1]$ for both electrodes and constrains the outputs $\bar{c}_j \in [0, 1]$ within the same order of magnitude.

Usually, the characteristic time-scale is chosen as $t_j^* = \frac{R_j^2}{D_j}$ to avoid numerical instabilities caused by the small order of magnitude of diffusivities in the dimensional PDE in Eq. (1), but as we vary diffusivities D_j in both electrodes independently from each other during training, this approach does not suffice here. Instead, we sample temporal coordinates uniformly from the nondimensionalized time coordinate of the negative electrode defined by $\bar{t} = \bar{t}_n = t \cdot \frac{D_n}{R_n^2}$ and account for the varying electrode-specific diffusivities, i.e., varying time-scales, by additional factors. These are simply derived via chain rules and applied when computing the time-derivatives via automatic differentiation during training as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{c}_p}{\partial \bar{t}_p} = \frac{\partial \bar{c}_p}{\partial t} \cdot \frac{\partial t}{\partial \bar{t}_p} = \frac{\partial \bar{c}_p}{\partial t} \cdot \frac{D_n^* R_n^2}{D_p^* R_n^2}, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{c}_j(D_j)}{\partial \bar{t}_{D_j}} = \frac{\partial \bar{c}_j(D_j^*)}{\partial \bar{t}_j} \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{t}_j}{\partial \bar{t}_{D_j}} = \frac{\partial \bar{c}_j(D_j^*)}{\partial \bar{t}_j} \cdot \frac{D_j^*}{D_j}, \quad j \in \{n, p\}, \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{t}_{D_j} = t \cdot \frac{D_j}{R_j^2}$ is the diffusivity-specific time-scale and constants D_j^* are chosen according to their respective nominal values provided in Table A.1 of Appendix. In order to resolve the different orders of magnitude in the diffusivity parameter space appropriately, the corresponding inputs are rescaled from $D_j \in [0, 1]$ when computing the time-derivatives in Eq. (10) via

$$D_j = 10^{\log_{10}(D_j^{\text{min}}) + \bar{D}_j \cdot (\log_{10}(D_j^{\text{max}}) - \log_{10}(D_j^{\text{min}}))}. \quad (11)$$

Note, that the SPM could easily be nondimensionalized and trained for both electrodes independently, but as we aim for a neural network that can (a) be extended to more advanced, coupled LIB models in

the future and (b) predict all output quantities in a single forward pass, we aim to train outputs of both electrodes simultaneously in a single network explaining the need for this wholistic, less intuitive nondimensionalization approach. The corresponding residuals to be minimized during training are combined in the four loss components

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{PDE}, j} = \frac{1}{N_I \cdot N_\Omega} \sum_{m=0}^{N_I} \sum_{i=0}^{N_\Omega} \left| \frac{\partial \bar{c}_j(\bar{x}_i, I_m)}{\partial \bar{t}} - \frac{2}{\bar{r}} \frac{\partial \bar{c}_j(\bar{x}_i, I_m)}{\partial \bar{r}} - \frac{\partial^2 \bar{c}_j(\bar{x}_i, I_m)}{\partial \bar{r}^2} \right|^2, \quad (12)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{BC}, j}^{\text{min}} = \frac{1}{N_I \cdot N_{\text{BC}}} \sum_{m=0}^{N_I} \sum_{i=0}^{N_{\text{BC}}} \left| \frac{\partial \bar{c}_j(\bar{x}_i, I_m)}{\partial \bar{r}} \right|_{\bar{r}=0}^2, \quad (13)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{BC}, j}^{\text{max}} = \frac{1}{N_I \cdot N_{\text{BC}}} \sum_{m=0}^{N_I} \sum_{i=0}^{N_{\text{BC}}} \left| \frac{\partial \bar{c}_j(\bar{x}_i, I_m)}{\partial \bar{r}} - \frac{I_m(\bar{t}) r^*}{AL_j F D_j a_j c^*} \right|_{\bar{r}=1}^2, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{IC}, j} = \frac{1}{N_I \cdot N_{\text{IC}}} \sum_{m=0}^{N_I} \sum_{i=0}^{N_{\text{IC}}} \left| \bar{c}_j(\bar{x}_i, I_m) - \frac{c_j^0}{c^*} \right|_{\bar{r}=0}^2, \quad (15)$$

where the 4-d scalar inputs are defined as $\bar{x}_i := (\bar{r}, \bar{t}, \bar{D}_n, \bar{D}_p)_i$ and $I_m := (I(\bar{t}_1), I(\bar{t}_2), \dots, I(\bar{t}_{N_I}))_m$ for the sake of readability. Furthermore, N_Ω , N_{BC} and N_{IC} denote the amount of collocation points \bar{x}_i sampled within the whole 4-d input domain, the spatial boundaries, and at $\bar{r} = 0$, respectively. N_I denotes the batch size of the branch, i.e., the amount of functional inputs trained per epoch on all collocation points.

The nondimensionalized initial condition in Eq. (15) is enforced into the architecture via hard constraints as introduced by Lu et al. [25]. This is achieved by the following transformation on the output of the last layer of the neural network $\hat{c}_j(r, t)$:

$$\bar{c}_j^{\text{NN}}(r, t) = t \cdot \hat{c}_j(r, t) + \frac{c_j^0}{c^*}. \quad (16)$$

Consequently, Eq. (4) is fulfilled by design and the loss term (15) can be neglected within the training process, which simplifies the underlying optimization problem and empirically improves convergence throughout this work. Fig. 2 depicts a PI-DeepONet trained to minimize the composed and purely physics-driven loss given as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{j \in \{n, p\}} \lambda_{\text{PDE}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{PDE}, j} + \lambda_{\text{BC}}^{\text{min}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{BC}, j}^{\text{min}} + \lambda_{\text{BC}}^{\text{max}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{BC}, j}^{\text{max}}, \quad (17)$$

with individual loss weights λ_{PDE} , $\lambda_{\text{BC}}^{\text{min}}$, $\lambda_{\text{BC}}^{\text{max}}$ empirically determined as described in Appendix.

2.2.2. Architectural adaptations

In addition to the physics-informed training scheme introduced above, we propose two modifications with respect to the “Standard” architecture, which are highlighted in red and green in Fig. 2 and described in the following.

Spatio-Temporal Multi-Scale Fourier-Features (ST-MS-FF). Earlier work on PINNs revealed that the spectral bias within the Neural Tangent Kernel (NTK) of PINNs may cause convergence issues for problems with multi-scale behavior, as the high-frequency components of the solution may not be learned efficiently due to this bias, cf. [26,27]. In [28], Wang et al. propose the usage of multi-scale random Fourier features to address this and propose an architecture with separate embeddings for spatial and temporal coordinates also referred to as Spatio-Temporal Multi-Scale Fourier-Features (ST-MS-FF). Motivated by NTK theory, they show that random Fourier embeddings with appropriate frequencies allow PINNs to converge faster, especially when solutions with multi-scale behavior need to be learned. We adopt this idea in the trunk of PI-DeepONet in Fig. 2 and employ random Fourier feature embeddings via

$$\gamma_x(\bar{r}, \bar{D}_n, \bar{D}_p) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\left(\left(\bar{r} \quad \bar{D}_n \quad \bar{D}_p\right) \cdot \mathbf{A}\right) \\ \sin\left(\left(\bar{r} \quad \bar{D}_n \quad \bar{D}_p\right) \cdot \mathbf{A}\right) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

Fig. 2. Parametrized PI-DeepONet with two adaptions (highlighted in red and green) compared to the “Standard” PI-DeepONet architecture.

$$\gamma_i(\vec{t}) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\vec{t} \cdot \mathbf{B}) \\ \sin(\vec{t} \cdot \mathbf{B}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (19)$$

where all entries of $A \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times \frac{m_x}{2}}$ and $B \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times \frac{m_t}{2}}$ are randomly sampled from Gaussian distributions $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_A)$, $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_B)$ with zero mean and standard deviations $\sigma_A = 1$ and $\sigma_B = 10$, respectively. The choice of standard deviations affects the magnitude of frequencies included in γ_x and γ_t , respectively, and is motivated by the fact that solutions of the SPM tend to exhibit higher frequencies in time than in space. This holds true especially at the particle surfaces $r = R_j$, where the spatial gradients are proportional to the — potentially high-frequent — current profile $I(t)$, cf. Eq. (3). The dynamics along the radial dimension, however, are dominated by the diffusion process within the particles causing solutions to exhibit comparatively low frequencies in space. Note that the inclusion of diffusivities into the spatial Fourier features in Eq. (18) is not a crucial requirement but led to minor convergence improvements within our studies. In contrast to [28], the spatio-temporal Fourier feature embeddings γ_x and γ_t are passed through separate networks NN_x^c and NN_t^c in our work as separate weights \mathbf{W}_ℓ^j and biases \mathbf{b}_ℓ^j are used in the forward pass

$$\mathbf{H}_{x,1} = \phi(\mathbf{W}_1^x \cdot \gamma_x + \mathbf{b}_1^x), \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{t,1} = \phi(\mathbf{W}_1^t \cdot \gamma_t + \mathbf{b}_1^t), \quad (21)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{x,\ell} = \phi(\mathbf{W}_\ell^x \cdot \mathbf{H}_{x,\ell-1} + \mathbf{b}_\ell^x), \quad \text{for } \ell = 2, \dots, n_{\text{layers}}, \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{t,\ell} = \phi(\mathbf{W}_\ell^t \cdot \mathbf{H}_{t,\ell-1} + \mathbf{b}_\ell^t), \quad \text{for } \ell = 2, \dots, n_{\text{layers}}, \quad (23)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{x,\ell}$ denotes the output of the ℓ th trainable layer of the respective subnetwork NN_x^c or NN_t^c and ϕ denotes the activation function. Consequently, the column dimensions $\frac{m_x}{2}$, $\frac{m_t}{2}$ of matrices A and B are determined by the number of nodes m_x and m_t in the first hidden layer of the respective networks NN_x^c and NN_t^c , cf. Fig. 2.

Parametrized trunk. Recent work by Cho et al. [29] suggests the usage of a sophisticated PINN architecture for parametrized problems involving an input domain with physical coordinates and PDE parameters. Therein, coordinates and parameters are passed separately through two encoder networks, NN^c and NN^p , after which the latent representations are concatenated and passed through another network referred to as manifold network NN^m . We employ the same idea within the trunk of

PI-DeepONet in Fig. 2 by passing the diffusivities (D_n, D_p) and spatio-temporal coordinates (r, t) through separate encoder networks before merging them within the corresponding manifold network. Note, that if the aforementioned spatio-temporally split Fourier feature embeddings are applied, this results in two distinct networks for the coordinate space NN_x^c and NN_t^c , as visualized in Fig. 2.

The two aforementioned architectural adaptions can be enabled independently, yielding a nomenclature of four different types of parametrized PI-DeepONets that are defined in Table 1 for further reference in Section 4.

3. Design-of-Experiments (DoE) framework

This section describes the DoE framework that is presented as an academic example to motivate how PI-DeepONets can be used within common DoE methodologies. More specifically, this framework aims at the identification of solid phase diffusivities D_n and D_p as introduced for the SPM in Section 2.1 based on the model response. We choose those diffusivities as calibration parameters in this work for two reasons. First, their theoretical identifiability for the SPM has been shown by Bizeray et al. [30]. Second, there are reported practical difficulties of determining these diffusivities accurately as they depend significantly on the SOC and temperature in the short term, as well as degradation effects and SOH in the long term [15,23]. In combination with different use cases representing different sets of current profiles, i.e., experimental designs, this framework aims to analyze which experimental design maximizes the identifiability of solid phase diffusivities from given model outputs and is described more thoroughly in the following.

3.1. Fisher Information Matrix (FIM)

The Fisher Information Matrix (FIM) is a fundamental concept in statistics, information theory, and recently also in machine learning [31]. It indicates how much information an observable random variable, or in the case of a data set, a data point, contains about an unknown parameter vector θ . This can also be used to determine which unknown parameters in the parameter vector θ cannot be uniquely

Table 1

Nomenclature for different PI-DeepONet setups used in this work. The common prefix “PI-” is dropped for the sake of readability as all considered architectures are subject to the same physics-informed loss function.

	Standard	Fourier-DeepONet	Param-DeepONet	Param-Fourier-DeepONet
ST-MS-FF	✗	✓	✗	✓
Parametrized Trunk	✗	✗	✓	✓

determined with the data set at hand [32,33]. Mathematically, the FIM is defined as:

$$\mathbf{FIM}(\theta) = \int_0^T S_y^T(t, \theta) Q(t)^{-1} S_y(t, \theta) dt, \quad (24)$$

where $Q(t)$ is the covariance matrix of the measurement error and $S_y(t, \theta) = \nabla_{\theta} y(\theta)$ the sensitivity matrix of outputs y with respect to the parameters θ , cf. [6]. In the scope of this work, the unknown parameter vector is given as $\theta = (D_n, D_p)$ and the SPM describes vectors of lithium concentrations $c_n(r, t)$, $c_p(r, t)$ that depend on both diffusivities D_n, D_p and the applied current profile $I(t)$. The corresponding voltage is the most relevant, measurable information in the context of model parametrization and can be post-processed from the surface concentrations $c_j(R_j, t)$ in the SPM, see Eq. (5). Therefore, we define the vector of relevant output information in our setup as:

$$\mathbf{c}(D_n, D_p, I) = (c_n(R_n, t^k, D_n, I), c_p(R_p, t^k, D_p, I)), \quad (25)$$

where t^k is discretized uniformly in $[t^0 = 0, t^1, t^2, \dots, t^{600} = t_{\max}]$. The inclusion of the covariance of the measurement error $Q(t)$ in Eq. (24) would account for the fact that variations in the measurement error of a specific battery tester may affect the FIM and, consequently, the FIM-based DoE optimization in a realistic context. In [6], this covariance is predicted efficiently using a regression model. As our work is focused on introducing a general framework for fast and accurate approximation of sensitivity matrices $S_y(t, \theta)$ and does not yet aim at an optimal DoE for a specific tester, we assume no variation in the measurement error and, using Eqs. (24) and (25), approximate the FIM for given (D_n, D_p) and current profile I as follows:

$$\mathbf{FIM}(D_n, D_p, I) \approx \begin{bmatrix} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{c}}{\partial D_n} \right)^T \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{c}}{\partial D_n} \right) & \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{c}}{\partial D_n} \right)^T \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{c}}{\partial D_p} \right) \\ \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{c}}{\partial D_p} \right)^T \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{c}}{\partial D_n} \right) & \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{c}}{\partial D_p} \right)^T \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{c}}{\partial D_p} \right) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

The FIM helps to measure the accuracy with which parameters can be estimated. In particular, the Cramér-Rao bound states that the inverse of the Fisher Information Matrix provides a lower bound on the variance of any unbiased estimator of the parameters θ [34]. This means that the diagonal elements of the inverse FIM provide the smallest possible variances of the parameter estimates, therefore a higher value in the diagonal elements of the FIM corresponds to a lower error. On the other hand, non-diagonal elements represent the correlation between individual parameters, but as we consider two intrinsically independent parameters D_n, D_p within the SPM, these entries are expected to be negligible. As it is common practice in model-based DoE, see [35], the so-called D-optimality criterion can be formulated as:

$$D^{\text{opt}}(D_n, D_p, I) := \log(\det(\mathbf{FIM}(D_n, D_p, I))). \quad (27)$$

Maximizing this quantity corresponds to minimizing the error in the parameter estimation and can also be used as an objective when optimizing the DoE, i.e., trying to determine the experiment (i.e., current profile $I(t)$) that yields the lowest error for estimating (D_n, D_p) via:

$$\max_I D^{\text{opt}}(D_n, D_p, I). \quad (28)$$

3.1.1. FIM approximation via five-point stencil

To calculate the elements of the FIM as well as the resulting D-optimality in Eq. (27), partial derivatives of the surface concentration vector \mathbf{c} with respect to the vector of calibration parameters $\theta =$

(D_n, D_p) have to be evaluated. Using Finite Differences (FD) with a five-point stencil approximation, the first order derivatives can be approximated numerically via

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{c}}{\partial D_j} \approx \frac{1}{12\Delta D_j} (-\mathbf{c}(D_j + 2\Delta D_j) + 8\mathbf{c}(D_j + \Delta D_j) - 8\mathbf{c}(D_j - \Delta D_j) + \mathbf{c}(D_j - 2\Delta D_j)). \quad (29)$$

In this case, the underlying model needs to be solved four times for each parameter D_j , using perturbations of D_j at different stencil points, i.e., $D_j \pm \Delta D_j$ and $D_j \pm 2\Delta D_j$, where ΔD_j represents a small relative perturbation (e.g., $10^{-3} \cdot D_j$). In a more general scenario featuring a larger number of calibration parameters N and five-point stencil approximation, the model needs to be solved $4 \times N$ times, which can pose a challenge when analyzing computationally intensive models. In addition, the order of accuracy for numerical differentiation may depend on the model or current profiles being analyzed. An alternative approach is presented in [6] where local sensitivities $S_y(t, \theta)$ are rigorously computed by solving a corresponding system of differential algebraic equations (SDAEs) at each time step.

3.1.2. FIM approximation using trained PI-DeepONets

The possibility to use Automatic Differentiation (AD) [36] within PI-DeepONets allows for a fast approximation of partial derivatives of any outputs c_j with respect to inputs (r, t, D_n, D_p) . This can be used to quickly approximate the FIM as defined in (26) and — as opposed to the SDAE approach in [6] or Eq. (29) — does not incur further overhead other than one forward pass through the network followed by one Jacobian computation per output c_j in “reverse mode” AD. In Section 4, we validate this approximation with respect to a five-point stencil approximation based on a numerical reference and compare the inference times of the numerical approach in Eq. (29) with the inference times of AD through a trained PI-DeepONet.

3.2. Use cases

Three use cases with different experimental design libraries, i.e., current profiles $I_1(t), I_2(t), \dots, I_{N_{\text{train}}}(t)$, are introduced that differ in terms of the diversity in the considered current profiles. For a fair comparison in terms of Fisher-Information, all profiles are restricted to a fixed duration of $t_{\max} = 10$ min, which was chosen such that concentration profiles respect the stoichiometric limits at 0% and 100% SOC in all considered combinations of current profiles and diffusivity values.

Constant current discharge (CC): The most basic use case is represented by constant current (CC) discharge profiles with currents sampled uniformly between 0 and 5 Ampere (1C). Experiments with constant current cycles are frequently used in battery testing, e.g., in experiments related to aging and degradation mechanisms within LIBs [37].

Gaussian Random Fields (GRF): To evaluate the performance of PI-DeepONets on dynamic, time-dependent profiles, a second use case is introduced by current profiles that are described by Gaussian Random Fields (GRF). In this specific application, the 1-dimensional function $I(t)$ is generated from a Gaussian random process based on the covariance kernel

$$k(t_i, t_j) = \exp \left(- \frac{2 \sin^2 \left(\pi \frac{\|t_i - t_j\|_2}{p} \right)}{l^2} \right) \quad (30)$$

Fig. 3. Visualization of the three considered use cases and solution diversity at particle surfaces. Left: Three example current profiles $I_1(t)$, $I_2(t)$, $I_3(t)$ for each use case. Right: Reference solution from *PyBaMM* for anode surface concentration $c_n(r=R_n, t, I(t), D_n)$ for each exemplary profile and $D_n \in \{10^{-15}, 10^{-14}, 10^{-13}\}$.

with periodicity $p = t_{\max}$ and length scale l . The kernel describes how current values $I(t_i)$ and $I(t_j)$ are correlated based on their periodical similarity and GRF profiles of higher or lower frequencies could be obtained by adapting the length scale. For the scope of this work, we stick to a fixed length scale of $l = 0.1$ and refer to other work by Zhu et al. for an in-depth study on GRFs of varying frequencies being applied in DeepONets [38].

Pulse profiles: As a more relevant scenario in battery testing, we consider a set of pulse profiles of different pulse widths as the third and final use case. Pulse profiles consist of alternating phases of constant-current discharges and resting phases without any current, which is commonly referred to as Galvanostatic-Intermittent-Titration-Technique (GITT) and used to infer diffusion parameters in battery testing [39,40]. In contrast to the two previous use cases, only a discrete set of pulses is chosen to maintain an equal amount of charge being transferred within the considered time window of 10 min for a fair comparison of identifiability. Therefore, we select four pulse profiles with widths of 300, 150, 100 and 60 s, respectively, by which $t_{\max} = 600$ s is evenly divisible and each profile begins with a discharge phase at 0.5C.

In addition to varying these use-case specific input profiles during training of PI-DeepONet, diffusivities for cathode and anode are varied independently within the same range of $[10^{-15}, 10^{-13}] \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}}$ for both electrodes. Fig. 3 shows three exemplary profiles per use case as well as the corresponding diffusivity-dependent anode surface concentration obtained from the open-source battery modeling framework *PyBaMM* [41].

4. Results and discussion

In this section, we benchmark the accuracy of PI-DeepONets as SPM surrogate models for the introduced use cases and architectures and evaluate their potential for local and global DoE methodologies based on FIM analysis.

4.1. Surrogate model accuracy

To evaluate the capabilities of PI-DeepONets as surrogate models, the concentration profiles $c_j^{\text{NN}}(r, t)$, predicted with PI-DeepONets, are compared with concentration profiles $c_j^{\text{ref}}(r, t)$ obtained via *PyBaMM*. *PyBaMM* is used to solve the SPM with Finite-Differences based on

the same parameter set used for training of PI-DeepONets, cf. Table A.1 in Appendix. In order to prevent inaccurate numerical results for small diffusivities with large spatial gradients at the particle surface, the discretization scheme in *PyBaMM* was setup sufficiently fine with 1001 points in space and 101 points in time. The accuracy in the 2-dimensional spatio-temporal domain is reported via the Mean-Absolute-Error (MAE) of point-wise concentrations as arithmetic mean over a grid of $N_r = 21$ points in space and $N_t = 101$ points in time. Furthermore, we evaluate the accuracy at the particle surfaces over time via a normalized Mean-Absolute-Percentage-Error (NMAPE^{surf}), as this provides a better intuition on the prediction capabilities of derived external variables like the SOC or voltage response, cf. Eq. (5). The normalization aims at a fair comparison of different use cases that may span different orders of magnitudes in their respective concentration profiles depending on the applied currents profiles and diffusivity values, see Fig. 3. As the voltage described by Eq. (5) is the most relevant quantity for practical applications, its Root-Mean-Squared-Error (RMSE) is reported here as well.

$$\text{NMAPE}^{\text{surf}} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j \in \{n, p\}} \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{i=0}^{N_t} \frac{|c_j^{\text{NN}}(R_j, t_i) - c_j^{\text{ref}}(R_j, t_i)|}{\max(c_j^{\text{ref}}(R_j, t)) - \min(c_j^{\text{ref}}(R_j, t))} \cdot 100 \% , \quad (31)$$

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j \in \{n, p\}} \frac{1}{N_r N_t} \sum_{l=0}^{N_r} \sum_{i=0}^{N_t} |c_j^{\text{NN}}(r_l, t_i) - c_j^{\text{ref}}(r_l, t_i)| , \quad (32)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{i=0}^{N_t} |V(c^{\text{NN}}, t_i) - V(c^{\text{ref}}, t_i)|^2} , \quad (33)$$

where the dependency of concentrations on applied current profiles $I(t)$ and diffusivities $(D_n, D_p)_k$ has been omitted for the sake of readability. Furthermore, to obtain scalar, comparable performance metrics for individual trainings of parametrized PI-DeepONets, both metrics are averaged over a logarithmically spaced grid of $11^2 = 121$ diffusivity tuples $(D_n, D_p)_k \in [10^{-15}, 10^{-13}]^2$ and the use case specific set of test current profiles $I_1(t), I_2(t), \dots, I_{N_{\text{test}}}(t)$ as follows:

$$\text{NMAPE}_{\text{avg}}^{\text{surf}} = \frac{1}{121 \cdot N_{I_{\text{test}}}} \sum_{k=1}^{121} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{I_{\text{test}}}} \text{NMAPE}^{\text{surf}}((D_n, D_p)_k, I_l(t)) , \quad (34)$$

$$\text{MAE}_{\text{avg}} = \frac{1}{121 \cdot N_{I_{\text{test}}}} \sum_{k=1}^{121} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{I_{\text{test}}}} \text{MAE}((D_n, D_p)_k, I_l(t)) , \quad (35)$$

Fig. 4. Accuracy evolution during training of “Standard” parametrized PI-DeepONet for each considered use case. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

$$\text{RMSE}_{\text{avg}} = \frac{1}{121 \cdot N_I^{\text{test}}} \sum_{k=1}^{121} \sum_{l=1}^{N_I^{\text{test}}} \text{RMSE}((D_n, D_p)_k, I_l(t)). \quad (36)$$

As a first benchmark, the “Standard” architecture of PI-DeepONets, cf. Table 1, is trained and evaluated with respect to its accuracy as surrogate model for the SPM while generalizing over different current profiles and diffusivity values. After spending significant resources for the tuning of hyperparameters — most notable network sizes, learning rates and collocation points — the most successful training runs in terms of $\text{NMAPE}_{\text{avg}}^{\text{surf}}$ are shown in Fig. 4 via the corresponding evolution of accuracy metrics throughout training. Both CC and GRF profiles can be approximated with an error below 2% $\text{NMAPE}_{\text{avg}}^{\text{surf}}$ after a few hours of training, which can be decreased further with additional training time to 0.41% and 0.30%, respectively. However, significantly more challenges arise when training non-smooth pulse profiles where an average error of around 2% remains even for longer training attempts. The corresponding plots for the MAE_{avg} and RMSE_{avg} show similar trends across training but also highlight the difficulties of comparing these different use cases within a non-normalized metric. This is most notable for the CC use case that yields comparatively large errors in terms of concentration MAE and voltage RMSE although the corresponding surface concentration predictions are relatively accurate. Hence, we focus on the $\text{NMAPE}_{\text{avg}}^{\text{surf}}$ for the following benchmarks of physics-informed training and, later on, base our evaluation of FIM predictions on training checkpoints that perform well in this metric.

In Fig. 5, an exemplary profile was chosen randomly for each use case and evaluated in terms of accuracy throughout the discretized diffusivity domain $(D_n, D_p)_k$, with $k = 1, 2, \dots, 121$. While most areas of the parameter domain are resolved accurately with an $\text{NMAPE}_{\text{avg}}^{\text{surf}}$ far below 1%, we repeatedly observe larger errors towards the upper limits of the diffusivity domain, which is observable in all use-cases

but most notable for pulse profiles, e.g., in the respective surface concentrations in the bottom right plots of Fig. 5. One explanation for this phenomenon may be that the sharp edges in the corresponding time-dependent Neumann boundary condition in Eq. (3) are scaled by the diffusivity value. This may cause an imbalance within the resulting loss terms in Eqs. (12)–(14) in this generalized training approach. Another reason might be an insufficient sampling density in the 4-dimensional input domain (r, t, D_n, D_p) with diffusivities spanning two orders of magnitude. Despite our logarithmic sampling approach via Eq. (11), this might benefit inaccuracies at the boundaries of the diffusivity domain due to extrapolation.

In order to improve both model accuracy and convergence speed, the architectural adaptations introduced in Section 2 are consequently benchmarked for the three use cases. For a fair comparison with the “Standard” architecture, all architectures are trained for a fixed number of 250k epochs and network sizes are adjusted such that all architectures contain comparable amounts of trainable variables within each use case, cf. Table A.2 in Appendix. To reduce random effects and detect outliers that may occur due to the non-deterministic nature of neural networks (e.g., due to random initialization of weights and biases), a minor grid search was executed for each use case and each architecture based on two rather sensitive hyperparameters. First, the learning rate, which limits the step size throughout the optimization process, and second, the batch size of the function space inputs in the branch net, i.e., the amount of functions $I_1(t), I_2(t), \dots, I_{N_I}(t)$ being sampled and trained on all collocation points per epoch. Fig. 6 shows the results in terms of $\text{NMAPE}_{\text{avg}}^{\text{surf}}$ with boxplots highlighting maxima, minima, as well as first, second (median) and third quartiles while outliers are plotted as dots. In the CC use case, accuracy decreases occasionally with the addition of Fourier features (orange), which can be explained by the fact that the CC use case contains

Fig. 5. (a): Exemplary profiles chosen randomly for each use-case. (b): Profile-specific accuracy of “Standard” PI-DeepONet resolved in the diffusivity domain (interpolation with 11×11 values). (c) and (d): Corresponding surface concentrations for $D_j \in \{10^{-15}, 10^{-14}, 10^{-13}\}$ in anode and cathode, respectively.

Fig. 6. Statistical benchmark results per use case for different architectures from Table 1 with varying learning rates and branch batch sizes highlighting the use case specific effects of adding architectural adaptations compared to “Standard”. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

solutions of very simple dynamics without any notable multi-scale behavior. Therefore, the addition of such transformations might indeed be harmful for the training process. The addition of a parametrized trunk (green and red) improves convergence significantly with the best results obtaining errors below 0.3% NMAPE_{surf}^{avg} in less than 5 GPU-hours. In the more dynamic use cases featuring GRF and pulse profiles, notable improvements seem to be related mainly to the addition of Fourier features (orange and red) achieving errors below 0.4% and 2% NMAPE_{surf}^{avg}, respectively, in less than 8 GPU-hours. The addition of the parametrized trunk architecture on its own (green) seems less effective. In the case of pulse profiles, none of the proposed architectural adaptations yield similar levels of accuracy as observed for the CC and GRF profiles. It should be noted that the addition and combination of the proposed architectural adaptations lead to a significant amount of additional hyperparameters that could hardly be tuned exhaustively in the scope of this work. These include the size of the different subnetworks NN^p, NN^c, NN^m or standard deviations σ_A and σ_B for generating the randomized Fourier features among several other, generally sensitive hyperparameters in DeepONets, leaving room for further research and improvements on top of the current results.

4.2. FIM analysis

The parametrized PI-DeepONets evaluated in the previous section can be useful surrogate models in parameter identification tasks due to their fast inference times of several milliseconds and automatic differentiability. As these methodological advantages have already been demonstrated in other works related to PINNs for battery modeling [18, 21], the remainder of this section is focused on the applicability of such models in DoE methodologies based on FIM analysis. In order to compare the D-optimality predicted by PI-DeepONet (via AD) and PyBaMM (via Eq. (29)) quantitatively, we introduce a further Mean-Absolute-Percentage-Error and refer to the corresponding D-optimality as D_{NN}^{opt} and $D_{\text{ref}}^{\text{opt}}$, respectively:

$$\text{MAPE}^{D^{\text{opt}}}(D_n, D_p, I) = \frac{|D_{NN}^{\text{opt}} - D_{\text{ref}}^{\text{opt}}|}{D_{\text{ref}}^{\text{opt}}} \cdot 100\%, \quad (37)$$

$$\text{MAPE}_{\text{avg}}^{D^{\text{opt}}}(I) = \frac{1}{121} \sum_{k=1}^{121} \text{MAPE}^{D^{\text{opt}}}((D_n, D_p)_k, I). \quad (38)$$

Fig. 7. Local FIM analysis at $(D_n^*, D_p^*) = (3.3 \cdot 10^{-14} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}}, 4.0 \cdot 10^{-15} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}})$ based on trained PI-DeepONet (“NN”) and a five-point stencil applied on concentration profiles from *PyBaMM* (“Reference”).

All D-optimality based on PI-DeepONets, $D_{\text{NN}}^{\text{opt}}$ are inferred based on the respective final training checkpoint of the “Standard” architecture, cf. Fig. 4 in Section 4.1.

Local D-optimality. In Fig. 7, the use case specific current profiles are analyzed after training in terms of local D-optimality at the nominal diffusivity values of $D_n^* = 3.3 \cdot 10^{-14} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}}$ and $D_p^* = 4.0 \cdot 10^{-15} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}}$. This local analysis provides insight into how informative each profile is for inferring parameters D_n^* , D_p^* based on the corresponding surface concentration profiles in both anode and cathode. First, we observe for the CC profiles that parameter identifiability increases with the applied current, which is expected as higher currents yield larger gradients at the particle surface, i.e., increasing the impact of slight diffusivity changes. Second, we evaluate a set of 100 randomly generated GRF profiles in terms of their D-optimality and plot the three profiles with the highest, lowest, and median score in terms of D-optimality, respectively. Qualitatively, these numbers are intuitive as profiles with smaller currents and less net charge transferred are expected to be less informative/sensitive in terms of the corresponding surface concentration response. The quantitative comparison of $D_{\text{NN}}^{\text{opt}}$ and $D_{\text{ref}}^{\text{opt}}$ shows high agreement in the case of CC and GRF profiles, while the gradient information is not in line when analyzed for the considered pulse profiles. This might be linked to the reduced accuracy for pulse profiles reported in Section 4.1 but also to an insufficient approximation of gradients within the five-point stencils. Further analysis shows that the reference D-optimality $D_{\text{ref}}^{\text{opt}}$ are very sensitive with respect to the relative perturbation ΔD_j when applied to non-smooth pulse profiles,

which is demonstrated further in Fig. A.1 in Appendix. However, both predictions and references for all pulse profiles (discharging at 0.5C at a duty cycle of 0.5) yield higher D-optimality than the constant-current discharge at 0.25C = 1.25 A with the equivalent amount of charge transferred, backing up their usage in the aforementioned GITT experiments.

Global D-optimality. In the aforementioned work by Park et al. [6], local sensitivities $S_y(t, \theta)$ are computed for several reasons: First, to obtain a parameter grouping for parametrization, second, within the parameter estimation process via the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm and, finally, to obtain confidence intervals for the estimated parameters. The authors of this work as well as other aforementioned works [4,9] suggest that local sensitivities may be insufficient if the nominal values are far away from the true values. Furthermore, Chen et al. [23] have shown that the experimentally determined diffusivity parameters span many orders of magnitude throughout the SOC range and admit that the proposed scalar average value is a significant simplification. In the following, we emphasize the potential of PI-DeepONets in context of global DoE methodologies, as they can be used much more efficiently to compute sensitivities, i.e., FIMs, throughout the complete parameter domain when the nominal values are unavailable or uncertain. To validate this both quantitatively and qualitatively, Fig. 8, depicts the three previously identified GRF profiles of high, medium, and low local identifiability from Fig. 7, and the evolution of their respective D-optimality when varying each parameter independently. Although minor deviations can be observed towards the lower and

Fig. 8. Top: FIM analysis throughout diffusivity domain for three exemplary profiles based on the trained PI-DeepONet (“NN”) and a five-point stencil applied on results from PyBaMM (“Reference”). Bottom: Error histogram for a set of 100 randomized GRF profiles.

upper boundaries of the diffusivity domain, the gradient information obtained via AD on the trained PI-DeepONet agree closely with the numerical reference. Identifiability increases with decreasing diffusivities, which is expected as the spatial gradients at particle surfaces are scaled inversely by the respective diffusivity in Eq. (3). This is equally true for both electrodes and further confirmed by the corresponding local FIM entries and the 2D plots of D_{NN}^{opt} shown in Fig. A.2 in Appendix. Finally, a quantitative comparison based on the 100 randomized GRF profiles used in the local analysis from Fig. 7 also shows a high agreement in terms of the global metric $MAPE_{avg}^{D^{opt}}$ with average deviations below 0.5% for almost all profiles.

To quantify the speed-up potential in the case of two calibration parameters and GRF profiles as design candidates, Table 2 compares the inference times of PyBaMM and the five-stencil from Eq. (29) with the “Standard” PI-DeepONet after around 24 h of training, cf. Fig. 4. The resulting speedup of approximately 30 for the global FIM analysis, cf. second and third row of Table 2, is due to the fact that FIM gradients can be retrieved for many points in the parameter domain simultaneously within one AD step (batched AD). Hence, this speedup is expected to increase further if more parameters are added to the input domain or a computationally more expensive PDE like the DFN model would be used in both PyBaMM and training of PI-DeepONet. We also note that the inference time for the PI-DeepONet is affected by the underlying AD implementation of DeepXDE and its TensorFlow 1.x backend, cf. [42], which was not compared with more efficient options in the scope of this work.

5. Conclusion and outlook

The proposed PI-DeepONet is able to approximate solutions of the SPM for varying current profiles and a wide range of diffusivity values within milliseconds while achieving percentage errors below 0.3% in case of constant or GRF profiles and below 2% in case of non-smooth pulse profiles given adequate architectural adaptations. The training is done completely data-free and only based on the governing equations of the SPM. In addition to its fast inference times as generalized surrogate model, the trained PI-DeepONet can be used efficiently to infer gradient information that is frequently used in DoE methodologies based on Fisher-Information. The corresponding gradient information has been validated quantitatively using a numerical reference solution and a five-point stencil for the gradient approximation. The combination of

Table 2

Inference times for FIM approximation. Runtimes are affected by assuming a required discretization granularity of 11 values per parameter. Both PyBaMM and inference on the trained PI-DeepONet are executed on an Intel Core i7-8650U CPU.

	PyBaMM (5-point stencil from Eq. (29))	PI-DeepONet (AD)
FIM(θ^* , I^*) (local, fixed profile)	$N_\theta \cdot 4$ SPM solves ≈ 4 s ($N_\theta = 2$)	N_{out} · AD ≈ 0.6 s
FIM($(\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots)_k$, I^*) $k = 1, \dots, N_\theta^{11}$ (global, fixed profile)	$N_\theta^{11} \cdot 4$ SPM solves ≈ 242 s ($N_\theta = 2$)	N_{out} · AD (batched) ≈ 0.8 s
FIM($(\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots)_k$, I_l) $k = 1, \dots, N_\theta^{11}$, $l = 1, \dots, N_I$ (global, varying profiles)	$N_I \cdot N_\theta^{11} \cdot 4$ SPM solves ≈ 6.7 h ($N_\theta = 2$, $N_I = 100$)	$N_I \cdot N_{out}$ · AD (batched) ≈ 800 s ($N_I = 100$)

high accuracy and fast inference times indicate that PI-DeepONets can be impactful surrogate models in obscure, i.e., not uniquely identifiable, parameter estimation scenarios which require both an efficient model and efficient ways to analyze Fisher-Information to improve the experimental design.

Both GPU memory and time consumption during training pose practical limitations at the current state of work and room for improvement in accuracy was observed for non-smooth current profiles. In future research, both these issues should be tackled, e.g., by incorporating more advanced training schemes and architectures tailored towards the SPM and more advanced battery models. Efficiency improvements during training are likely to become more crucial as soon as more than two parameters are incorporated in the input domain as the curse of dimensionality would cause the number of required collocation points to increase exponentially. Recent work by Mandl et al. [43] addresses this issue and should be adapted for LIB-specific DeepONets as well. Future work is planned to employ the proposed methodology for the parametrization process of an actual LIB cell based on experimentally measured voltage data, which requires some modifications with respect to the current state of work. These include a voltage-based FIM definition, introduction of advanced battery models in the loss formulation, generalization over varying initial conditions, cf. [18], and the choice of model parameters and current profiles that are varied during training.

Table A.1
Cell specifications and parameters for the SPM as given by Chen et al. [23].

Parameter	Unit	Description	Anode ($j = n$)	Cathode ($j = n$)
Q_{nom}	[Ah]	Nominal cell capacity		5
A	[m ²]	Electrode surface area		0.1027
L_j	[m]	Electrode thickness	8.25e−5	7.56e−5
R_j	[m]	Electrode particle radius	5.86e−6	5.22e−6
$z_{0\%}$	[−]	Stoichiometry at 0% SOC	0.0279	0.9084
$z_{100\%}$	[−]	Stoichiometry at 100% SOC	0.9014	0.27
ϵ_j	[−]	Active material volume fraction	0.75	0.665
c_j^{max}	[$\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3}$]	Maximum concentration	33 133	63 104
a_j	[$\frac{1}{\text{m}}$]	Specific interfacial area	$3 \frac{\epsilon_a}{R_a}$	$3 \frac{\epsilon_p}{R_p}$
c_j^0	[$\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3}$]	Initial solid phase concentration	$z_{50\%} \cdot c_p^{\text{max}}$	$z_{50\%} \cdot c_n^{\text{max}}$
D_j	[$\frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}}$]	Solid phase lithium diffusivity	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-15}$
$c_{e,j}$	[$\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3}$]	Electrolyte concentration (const.)		1000
F	[$\frac{\text{C}}{\text{mol}}$]	Faraday's constant		96 485.33
R	[$\frac{\text{J}}{\text{mol K}}$]	Universal gas constant		8.31
T	[K]	Temperature		298.15
t_{max}	[min]	Length of time interval		10

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Philipp Brendel: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Igor Mele:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology. **Andreas Roskopf:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology. **Tomaž Katrašnik:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Vincent Lorentz:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

A.1. Parameters for the single-particle-model

Table A.1 describes all relevant parameters for the SPM as provided by Chen et al. [23].

A.2. Implementation details and hyperparameters

All variations of PI-DeepONets were implemented based on DeepXDE [42] with the TensorFlow 1.x backend. Trainings were executed and runtimes measured on an NVIDIA A100 GPU with 82 GB VRAM. Table A.2 describes all relevant hyperparameters that were used in the baseline results based on the “Standard” DeepONet architecture in Fig. 4. In addition, Table A.3 describes all parameters that were either changed with respect to Table A.2 or varied during the hyperparameter study in Fig. 6. Note that the corresponding trunk sizes of architectures with split spatio-temporal features (“F” or “PF” in Table A.3) are adapted to obtain similar total amounts of trainable parameters,

e.g., two split networks of size [3 · 40] instead of one shared network of size [3 · 60]. The increased amount of trainable parameters in case of pulse profiles is mainly due to the larger input dimension of the branch network, cf. Table A.2.

A.3. Sensitivity study on finite difference stencils

To understand the deviations between predictions and numerical calculations of D^{opt} for some pulse profiles in Fig. 7, a higher-order seven-point stencil is introduced for comparison as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{c}}{\partial D_j} \approx \frac{1}{60\Delta D_j} \left(-\mathbf{c}(D_j - 3\Delta D_j) + 9\mathbf{c}(D_j - 2\Delta D_j) - 45\mathbf{c}(D_j - \Delta D_j) + 45\mathbf{c}(D_j + \Delta D_j) - 9\mathbf{c}(D_j + 2\Delta D_j) + \mathbf{c}(D_j + 3\Delta D_j) \right), \quad (\text{A.1})$$

and the relative perturbations ΔD_j in Eqs. (29) and (A.1), are chosen from $\{5 \cdot 10^{-4}, 1 \cdot 10^{-3}, 2 \cdot 10^{-3}\}$. Fig. A.1 shows that the gradients in the CC profiles are insensitive with respect to the parameter perturbation, whereas the results for pulse profiles show larger deviations. These deviations are further emphasized in the higher-order seven-point stencil approximation scheme that yields similar tendencies. We conclude that the choice of stencil and especially its width affects the results in case of non-smooth pulse profiles quite heavily and no conclusive statement can be made about the accuracy of PI-DeepONet based on these references.

A.4. Parameter-specific identifiability

Instead of analyzing the FIM via its determinant, as realized by the D-optimality metric D^{opt} , the individual identifiability of each parameter is indicated by the diagonal entries of the FIM. Fig. A.2 depicts the corresponding FIMs for the three GRF profiles selected in the local FIM analysis with high, medium, and low identifiability, respectively, cf. Fig. 7 in Section 4. In combination with the corresponding visualization of $D_{\text{NN}}^{\text{opt}}$ in the 2D parameter domain below, it becomes evident that the parameter-specific identifiability mainly depends on the respective nominal values. As we have $D_p^* < D_n^*$, a higher identifiability is observed for D_p^* in this local scope. We emphasize, that these analyses would be expected to change qualitatively if the FIM was defined via the voltage response instead of surface concentrations, e.g., due to the SOC-dependent slope of the corresponding open-circuit-potentials, e.g., shown in the work by Bizeray et al. [30]. Post-processing voltages from concentration responses in an automatically differentiable

Table A.2
Hyperparameters used for baseline results with “Standard” architecture in Fig. 4.

Parameter	CC	GRF	Pulses
N_{Ω}	20k	5k	20k
N_{BC}	20k	5k	20k
$ N_I^{\text{train}} $	$N_I \cdot \text{Epochs}$	$N_I \cdot \text{Epochs}$	4
Sampling:	random $\in [0, 5]$ A	Random (Eq. (30))	Discrete (Section 3.2)
$ N_I^{\text{test}} $	5	9	4
Sampling:	{1, 2, 3, 4, 5} A	Random (Eq. (30))	Discrete (Section 3.2)
Epochs	1,000,000		
Activation Function	SiLU		
Initialization	Glorot uniform		
Initial Learning Rate (η_0)	$1 \cdot 10^{-3}$		
Exp. Learning Rate Decay	$\eta(\text{epoch}) = \eta_0 \cdot 0.8^{\frac{\text{epoch}}{1000}}$		
Batch Size - Branch N_I	8		4
Branch Input Dimension N_I	2	101	601
Branch Size ($n_{\text{layers}} \cdot n_{\text{nodes}}$)	$3 \cdot 20$		$3 \cdot 50$
Trunk Size ($n_{\text{layers}} \cdot n_{\text{nodes}}$)	$3 \cdot 60$		$5 \cdot 80$
Latent Output Dimension m	10		50
Multi-Output-Strategy [42]	Independent		
Loss Weights ($\lambda_{\text{PDE}}, \lambda_{\text{BC}}^{\text{min}}, \lambda_{\text{BC}}^{\text{max}}$)	(0.1, 0.01, 1)		

Table A.3
Varying hyperparameters used for architectural benchmarks in Fig. 6 with short notations for Standard (“S”), Fourier-DeepONet (“F”), Param-DeepONet (“P”) and Param-Fourier-DeepONet (“PF”). Trunk sizes for the parametrized trunks in “P” and “PF” are given as (NN^p, NN^r, NN^m) .

Parameter	CC	GRF	Pulses	
Epochs		250,000		
Initial learning rate (η_0)	$\in \{2 \cdot 10^{-3}, 1 \cdot 10^{-3}\}$	$\in \{1 \cdot 10^{-3}, 5 \cdot 10^{-4}\}$		
Exp. Learning rate decay	$\eta(\text{epoch}) = \eta_0 \cdot 0.8^{\frac{\text{epoch}}{250}}$			
Batch size - Branch N_I	$\in \{4, 8\}$		$\in \{2, 4\}$	
Trunk Sizes (# Total Trainable Param.)	“S”	$3 \cdot 60$ (22,642)	$5 \cdot 80$ (86,242)	(136,242)
	“F”	$2 \cdot [3 \cdot 40]$ (20,442)	$2 \cdot [5 \cdot 60]$ (90,162)	(140,162)
	“P”	$[3 \cdot 30, 3 \cdot 30, 3 \cdot 30]$ (21,982)	$[3 \cdot 50, 3 \cdot 80, 3 \cdot 50]$ (90,802)	(140,802)
	“PF”	$[3 \cdot 30, 2 \cdot [3 \cdot 20], 3 \cdot 30]$ (20,162)	$[3 \cdot 50, 2 \cdot [3 \cdot 60], 3 \cdot 50]$ (84,362)	(134,362)

Fig. A.1. Sensitivity of D^{opt} with respect to relative perturbation ΔD_j and order of finite-difference stencil for constant-current (top) and pulse profiles (bottom). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. A.2. Top: Visualization of local FIMs at (D_n^*, D_p^*) , predicted by “Standard” PI-DeepONet for current profiles I_{24}, I_{50}, I_{59} shown in Fig. 7. Bottom: Visualization of D-optimality throughout the parameter domain for the same three profiles.

manner, e.g., as demonstrated by Zheng et al. [18], would yield more realistic results for practical parameter identification scenarios and is planned in future work.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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